

TRANSLATION THEORIES AND TEXT TYPES

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Annotation: *The aim of this paper is to show the relevance that a correct interpretation of text types in the mother tongue has for the correct development of the translating activity by translator trainees. This paper briefly analyzes the results of a classroom activity in which students were asked to identify the text-type ascription of two texts.*

Key words: *text type, vocative text, translation, informative text, semantic translation.*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7622608>

Introduction. Translation is a very broad, complex and multi-faceted phenomenon, encompassing much more factors than it seems at first glance. It is not just copying the words from the original work while changing the language, but it consists of a careful selection of appropriate phrases and expressions, combining them together in a skillful way while taking into consideration numerous aspects, one of them being the text type.

Text may also be defined as a certain communicative action of a complex structure that functions in a specific semantic space and is to fulfill specific functions, for instance: informative, esthetic, pragmatic function, etc.. It is this function that determines the text's characteristic features. Therefore, according to this definition, a text is perceived not only as a result of a certain effort of the sender, but also, and above all, as a product that is able to fulfill its communicative function in the process of the appropriate interpretation by a reader.

Main body. According to Neubert, text types are socially effective, efficient, and appropriate moulds into which the linguistic material available in the system of a language is recast.

Sager remarks that text types developed as patterns of messages for certain communicative situations. When writing a specific message, a person first of all thinks about the text type that would be appropriate for the given occasion as well as for the content of the message, and only then formulates the message itself. Repetitions of messages in certain circumstances have created particular expectations and conventions of what is appropriate for the given occasion. However, the notion of a text type is more complex than that. Whereas the majority of people associate a text type with a certain content, for instance film review, police report, recipe, it frequently happens that the same content may permit a variety of text types. Sager concludes that text types have evolved from

conventionalized communicative situations. As a result of this and since they arise from common relationships between the author and the reader, they are capable of conveying messages unambiguously. Their other characteristic features are topic and mode of expression.

In vocative texts, if a communicative translation is pursued then equivalent effect will be sought. This type of texts usually aimed at persuasion and behavior influence. Therefore, it will be so much important to transfer the meaning that adapts –or with equivalent effect- in the TL culture.

Informative texts translations are also desired to reflect equivalent effect in its readers only in the vocative parts within these informative texts, equivalent effect once again becomes essential, as the persuasion and influence component is present. However, if the TL and SL culture are remote, then equivalent effect will be unachievable. Therefore, more generic translation is suitable in order to ease comprehension. Most texts that are directed to a wide public audience the translator will seek equivalent effect in his/her translation.

Semantic translations on the other hand, are usually directed towards specific readers, mostly those who are familiar with the text's background. It therefore carries less equivalence, and Newmark explains this by saying that "the more cultural (the more local, the more remote in time and space) a text, the less is equivalent effect even conceivable...". According to this we can agree with Newmark statement that "Certainly, the more 'universal' the text ...the more a broad equivalent effect is possible".

Newmark's puts a very important view, by dividing texts into universal and local, which expressive, vocative and informative texts can fall into easily. This will ease the process of matching between the text type and translation approach. *Expressive texts* content will mostly be under local texts, approached formally and semantically as it is composed of culturally specific components e.g. certain literature.

Vocative texts on the other hand can be categorised under universal (depending on degree of universality) and approached communicatively and dynamically, as it is aimed at a broader audience and for persuasion purposes, and so allow the translator more freedom (dynamic) to transmit the equivalent effect of the text.

Finally, *informative texts* approach will vary according to content and context. If there is vocative aspects included, that vocative part will also be approached dynamically with the aim of reaching equivalence. But, the informative part approach depends on the cultural proximity between the TL and SL. The further away the two cultures are from each other, the less equivalent effect there will be. This is because it is almost impossible to find equivalence if generic terms are used to ease understanding of the translation.

Conclusion

There has been a long debate within the field of translation studies about whether it is possible to classify texts and whether such a classification is useful for practising translators.

First of all, the very notion of text type is so broad that it can comprise a large number of text-form variants. For instance, texts as varied as legal acts, technical instructions, sermons, political speeches and advertisements can all be included in the text type "instruction". The second substantial difficulty related to text typologies is the issue of hybridisation, that is the fact that a certain text often includes several different types.

Nevertheless, text typologies and their role in identifying the text purpose and function as well as the author's intention are still perceived as valuable tools for translators, enabling them to establish the appropriate hierarchy of equivalence levels and choose such strategies that would best serve to preserve the given purpose, function and intention.

List of literature

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